

A NOTE ON INCOMPLETE LEONARDO NUMBERS

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Abstract

In this paper, incomplete Leonardo numbers are defined, their recurrence relations are analyzed, and some properties and generating functions of this sequence of integers are studied.

1. Introduction and Background

The Fibonacci sequence $\{F_n\}_n$ is one of the most well-known sequences of positive integers. This sequence is defined by the following recurrence relation:

$$F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}, \quad n \geq 2, \quad (1)$$

with $F_0 = 0$ and $F_1 = 1$.

For $n \geq 0$, the Binet formula of Fibonacci numbers is given by

$$F_n = \frac{\Phi^n - \Psi^n}{\Phi - \Psi}, \quad (2)$$

where $\Phi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ and $\Psi = \frac{1-\sqrt{5}}{2}$ are the roots of the associated quadratic equation $r^2 - r - 1 = 0$ of recurrence relation (1).

The explicit formula of F_n (see, for example, [5, p. 21]) is given by

$$F_n = \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor} \binom{n-1-j}{j}. \quad (3)$$

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This formula will be used in the next section when a new sequence of integers is introduced.

Recently, Catarino and Borges [1] considered the Leonardo sequence, an integer sequence related to the Fibonacci and Lucas sequences. In this work, the authors dedicated their research to the Leonardo sequence, establishing sums and products formulae and also the respective Binet formula. Several identities are presented and a generating function was created in this work.

In order not to be confused with the Lucas number, throughout this text we will adopt the expression Le_n to denote the n th Leonardo number and consequently the Leonardo sequence will be denoted by $\{Le_n\}_{n=0}^\infty$. This sequence is defined by the recurrence relation

$$Le_n = Le_{n-1} + Le_{n-2} + 1, \quad n \geq 2, \tag{4}$$

with the initial conditions $Le_0 = Le_1 = 1$. This sequence is entry A001595 of the On-line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences [9].

According to Proposition 2.2 of [1], the Leonardo and Fibonacci numbers are related as follows:

$$Le_n = 2F_{n+1} - 1, \quad n \geq 0. \tag{5}$$

By using the Binet formula for Fibonacci numbers (2), the Binet formula for Leonardo numbers can be easily established. Thus, we have the following formula:

$$Le_n = 2 \left(\frac{\Phi^{n+1} - \Psi^{n+1}}{\Phi - \Psi} \right) - 1 = \frac{\Phi(2\Phi^n - 1) - \Psi(2\Psi^n - 1)}{\Phi - \Psi}, \quad n \geq 0, \tag{6}$$

where Le_n is the n th Leonardo number, $\Phi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$ and $\Psi = \frac{1-\sqrt{5}}{2}$.

The research into these types of numerical sequences has been developed in several ways, one of which has considered the *incomplete* numbers and polynomials of Fibonacci, Lucas and Tribonacci, among others. For studies about the incomplete Fibonacci and Lucas numbers and their generating functions and properties, see for example [4] and [6], and for the incomplete Tribonacci numbers, see for example [8] and [13]. The incomplete generalized Fibonacci and Lucas numbers are presented in [2] and the incomplete generalized Jacobsthal and Jacobsthal-Lucas numbers in [3]. We may also refer to [7], [10], [11] and [12].

In this paper, we will define the *incomplete* Leonardo numbers and present the recurrence equations and other properties that these numbers satisfy. In section 2, we present the referred sequence and the respective recurrence relations. In section 3, we describe some properties of this sequence. Finally, in the last section we provide a brief overview of how the respective generating function can be determined.

2. The Incomplete Leonardo Numbers

In this section we present a new integer sequence which is related with the explicit formula of F_n given in (3). With this formula, taking into account (5), we have the following definition.

Definition 1. *The incomplete Leonardo numbers are defined by*

$$Le_n^l := 2 \sum_{j=0}^l \binom{n-j}{j} - 1, \quad (0 \leq l \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor; n \in \mathbb{N}_0). \tag{7}$$

Note that

$$Le_n^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor} = Le_n$$

and some special cases of (7) are:

$$\begin{aligned} Le_n^0 &= 1, \quad (n \geq 0); \\ Le_n^1 &= 2n - 1, \quad (n \geq 2); \\ Le_n^2 &= n^2 - 3n + 5, \quad (n \geq 4); \\ Le_n^{\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor} &= \begin{cases} Le_n - 2, & (n \text{ even}) \\ Le_n, & (n \text{ odd}) \end{cases} \quad (n \geq 1). \end{aligned}$$

In the next result we present a recurrence relation verified by this sequence of numbers, followed by other results which reveal some properties of these numbers.

Proposition 1. *For any natural number n , the incomplete Leonardo numbers satisfy the following recurrence equation:*

$$Le_{n+2}^{l+1} = Le_{n+1}^{l+1} + Le_n^l + 1, \quad (0 \leq l \leq \frac{n-1}{2}; n \in \mathbb{N}). \tag{8}$$

Proof. By Definition 1 we get

$$\begin{aligned} Le_{n+1}^{l+1} + Le_n^l + 1 &= 2 \sum_{j=0}^{l+1} \binom{n+1-j}{j} - 1 + 2 \sum_{j=0}^l \binom{n-j}{j} - 1 + 1 \\ &= 2 \sum_{j=0}^{l+1} \left[\binom{n+1-j}{j} + \binom{n+1-j}{j-1} \right] - 1 \\ &= 2 \sum_{j=0}^{l+1} \binom{n+2-j}{j} - 1 \\ &= Le_{n+2}^{l+1}, \end{aligned}$$

as required. □

Proposition 2. *For any natural number n , the recurrence relation of the incomplete Leonardo numbers Le_n^l given in (8) can be transformed into the non-homogeneous recurrence equation given below:*

$$Le_{n+2}^l = Le_{n+1}^l + Le_n^l + 1 - 2 \binom{n-l}{l}, \quad (0 \leq l \leq \frac{n-1}{2}). \tag{9}$$

Proof. By Proposition 2.1 and Definition 1 we get the following:

$$\begin{aligned} Le_{n+2}^l - Le_{n+1}^l - Le_n^l - 1 &= (Le_{n+1}^l + Le_n^{l-1} + 1) - Le_{n+1}^l - Le_n^l - 1 \\ &= Le_n^{l-1} - Le_n^l \\ &= 2 \sum_{j=0}^{l-1} \binom{n-j}{j} - 1 - 2 \sum_{j=0}^l \binom{n-j}{j} + 1 \\ &= 2 \left[\sum_{j=0}^{l-1} \binom{n-j}{j} - \sum_{j=0}^l \binom{n-j}{j} \right] \\ &= 2 \left[- \binom{n-l}{l} \right] \\ &= -2 \binom{n-l}{l}, \end{aligned}$$

as required. □

We also note that from (7), we can deduce $Le_n^l = 2F_{n+1}^l - 1$ and in Table 1 we present a few incomplete Leonardo numbers.

$n \setminus l$	$l = 0$	$l = 1$	$l = 2$	$l = 3$	$l = 4$
$n = 0$	1				
$n = 1$	1				
$n = 2$	1	3			
$n = 3$	1	5			
$n = 4$	1	7	9		
$n = 5$	1	9	15		
$n = 6$	1	11	23	25	
$n = 7$	1	13	33	41	
$n = 8$	1	15	45	65	67

Table 1: The incomplete Le_n^l for $0 \leq n \leq 8$

3. Some Properties of the Incomplete Leonardo Sequence

In this section we present other properties involving the incomplete Leonardo numbers. These properties are stated in the results below.

Proposition 3. *For any natural numbers n and s , the following identity holds:*

$$Le_{n+2s}^{l+s} = \sum_{i=0}^s \binom{s}{i} Le_{n+i}^{l+i} + 1, \quad 0 \leq l \leq \frac{n-s}{2}. \tag{10}$$

Proof. We prove this by induction on s . It is clear that for $s = 1$, (10) holds. Now suppose that the result is true for all $j < s + 1$ and we shall prove it for $s + 1$. Then using some combinatorial properties and Proposition 2.1, we have the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \binom{s+1}{i} Le_{n+i}^{l+i} + 1 &= \sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \left[\binom{s}{i} + \binom{s}{i-1} \right] Le_{n+i}^{l+i} + 1 \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \binom{s}{i} Le_{n+i}^{l+i} + \sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \binom{s}{i-1} Le_{n+i}^{l+i} + 1 \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \binom{s}{i} Le_{n+i}^{l+i} + \binom{s}{s+1} Le_{n+s+1}^{l+s+1} + \sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \binom{s}{i-1} Le_{n+i}^{l+i} + 1 \\ &= Le_{n+2s}^{l+s} + \binom{s}{s+1} Le_{n+s+1}^{l+s+1} + \sum_{i=-1}^s \binom{s}{i} Le_{n+i+1}^{l+i+1} + 1 \\ &= Le_{n+2s}^{l+s} + \sum_{i=0}^s \binom{s}{i} Le_{n+i+1}^{l+i+1} + 1 \\ &= Le_{n+2s}^{l+s} + Le_{n+2s+1}^{l+s+1} + 1 \\ &= Le_{n+2(s+1)}^{l+(s+1)}, \end{aligned}$$

as required. □

Now let us consider the sum of s consecutive elements of the l th column of the array shown in Table 1.

Proposition 4. *For any natural numbers n and s , and given l such that $n \geq 2l + 2$, we have*

$$\sum_{i=0}^{s-1} Le_{n+i-1}^l + s = Le_{n+s}^{l+1} - Le_n^{l+1}. \tag{11}$$

Proof. We proceed by induction on s . The sum (11) is true for $s = 1$ (see Proposition 2.1). Now suppose that the result is valid for all $j < s$ and we shall prove it for s . Using Proposition 2.1, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} Le_{n+s+1}^{l+1} - Le_n^{l+1} &= (Le_{n+s}^{l+1} + Le_{n+s-1}^l + 1) - Le_n^{l+1} \\ &= (Le_{n+s}^{l+1} - Le_n^{l+1}) + Le_{n+s-1}^l + 1 \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=0}^{s-1} Le_{n+i-1}^l + s \right) + Le_{n+s-1}^l + 1 \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=0}^{s-1} Le_{n+i-1}^l + Le_{n+s-1}^l \right) + (s + 1) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^s Le_{n+i-1}^l + (s + 1) \end{aligned}$$

and the result follows. □

4. Generating Function of the Incomplete Leonardo Numbers

The generating function

$$GF_{Le}(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} Le_j^l t^j$$

of the incomplete Leonardo numbers can be obtained by taking into account the generating function $R_k(t) := \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} F_k(j)t^j$ of the incomplete Fibonacci numbers (see [6, p. 529]),

$$R_k(t) = t^{2k+1} \left(\frac{(F_{2k} + F_{2k-1}t)(1-t)^{k+1} - t^2}{(1-t)^{k+1}(1-t-t^2)} \right),$$

and the fact that $Le_n^l = 2F_{n+1}^l - 1$. Some studies related to the incompleteness of other sequences (incomplete k -Fibonacci, k -Lucas, k -Pell, k -Pell-Lucas sequences - see the works [2], [3], [4], among others), used the following lemma stated in [6] in order to find the respective generating function of each sequence.

Lemma 1. *Let $\{s_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ be a complex sequence satisfying the following nonhomogeneous recurrence relation:*

$$s_n = as_{n-1} + bs_{n-2} + r_n \quad (n > 1),$$

where a and b are complex numbers and $\{r_n\}$ is a given complex sequence. Then the generating function $U(t)$ of the sequence $\{s_n\}$ is

$$U(t) = \frac{G(t) + s_0 - r_0 + (s_1 - s_0a - r_1)t}{1 - at - bt^2},$$

where $G(t)$ denotes the generating function of $\{r_n\}$.

The construction of a sequence $\{s_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ plays a crucial role for finding the respective generating function.

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